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Missed Nursing Care in Intensive Care Units: A Bibliometric Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study conducts a bibliometric analysis of missed nursing care in intensive care units.

Methods: A search in the Web of Science database using the keywords "Missing nursing care," "Nursing care rationing," "Care left undone," "missed care," "miss care," and "intensive care" yielded 951 studies. After final filtering, 951 studies published between 2019 and 2023 were selected. Data analysis was performed using RStudio Bibliometrix and Vosviewer 1.6.19 programs.

Results: A total of 951 documents from 10 different countries and 165 different sources were reviewed, of which 758 are research articles. Publications per year were as follows: 144 in 2019, 226 in 2020, 172 in 2021, 210 in 2022, and 199 in 2023. The United States has a dominant position with 271 articles, and the "Journal of Nursing Management" is the most prolific journal. The United States also leads substantially in citations, with 1,157 citations recorded. Critical terms highlighted include 'patient safety,' 'missed nursing care,' and 'nursing care.'

Implications: The significance of missed nursing care is growing in clinical practice settings. There is diversity among different countries and sources regarding this issue, yet the United States is notably prominent in this field.

Keywords: Missed nursing care, Bibliometric analysis, Intensive care units, missed care, miss care.

Introduction

Intensive care units (ICUs) are highly complex environments where critically ill patients receive advanced care and treatment facilitated by various technological tools and devices (1). This intricate and critical setting often becomes a source of stress for both patients and healthcare professionals (2). Nurses managing the care of ICU patients encounter numerous stressors stemming from the unit's unique characteristics while simultaneously addressing the concerns of patients and their families. They bear the physical and psychological burdens of caring for critically ill individuals, must handle high-knowledge situations, ensure patient safety, provide essential materials, and maintain these materials in a ready-to-use state.

Nursing care, a central concept of professional nursing, is intrinsic to the nursing discipline (3). Nursing care must be administered by competent nurses who can deliver quality, comprehensive care (4). The quality of nursing care varies across healthcare institutions (5). Access to quality nursing care is both a right for patients and a responsibility for nurses, with the overall quality of healthcare services being influenced by the level of nursing care provided. Cost-effective nursing care can also enhance the quality of nursing services (6). Essential nursing care may occasionally be overlooked in daily practices, posing threats to patient safety (7). The failure to provide adequate nursing care introduces the concept of unmet nursing care needs.

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medjeur.com/congress

Oral Presentation-15 (continue)

The term "Missing Nursing Care (MNC)" was first defined by Kalisch in 2006 through qualitative research as the neglect or postponement of all or part of the necessary care (8). Missing Nursing Care is variously described as "missed care," "unmet care," "left behind care," "incomplete care," "unfinished care," and "deferred care." For clarity in this bibliometric analysis, the term "Missing Nursing Care" will be used.

Recent research has highlighted a direct correlation between Missing Nursing Care and conditions such as heart failure, acute myocardial infarction, phlebitis, pressure ulcers, and urinary system infections, as well as outcomes like reduced patient satisfaction, increased falls, extended hospital stays, delays in discharge, physical disabilities, and even higher mortality rates (9-14). Furthermore, Missing Nursing Care has emerged as an international issue with significant safety and cost implications for patients and health systems (15,16). As a result, the topic of Missing Nursing Care has gained increasing attention in scholarly literature, with studies focusing on its prevalence and causes (9, 17), associated factors (10,11), influencing conditions (18), and its impact on both patients and nurses (19).

Missing Nursing Care can manifest at any stage of the care process (20). Factors such as long working hours (21), increased workload, the professional experience of nurses (21, 22), high patient-to-nurse ratios (23), limited resources and equipment (21,22), and inadequate nurse/assistant ratios (24) compel nurses to prioritize immediate tasks over others that can be postponed (25). These factors can lead to delays or the non-provision of specific nursing interventions (22).

Studies conducted around the globe show that necessary nursing care is often missed for various reasons, indicating that Missing Nursing Care is a global concern and prompting researchers worldwide to investigate this issue further. This study discusses Missing Nursing Care in intensive care units, aiming to enhance our understanding of its significance, potential contributions in this area, its international definitions, and its scholarly contributions.

Methods

Figure 1. Flowchart of the search strategy.

Using the Web of Science database, we searched with the keywords "Missing nursing care," "Nursing care rationing," "Care left undone," "missed care," "miss care," and "intensive care." As of November 25, 2023, our search yielded 951 studies published between 2019 and 2023. We analyzed these 951 studies using RStudio Bibliometrix and Vosviewer 1.6.19 software, resulting in the below findings.

2nd European Congress of Health Sciences

May 4-5, 2024 - Bristow, VA / USA (ONLINE)
medjeur.com/congress

Oral Presentation-15 (continue)

Findings

Between 2019 and 2023, a total of 951 documents from 165 different sources on intensive care units and missed nursing care were reviewed. The majority of these documents are full-text articles, totaling 758. Editorial materials and reviews follow with 30 and 103 items, respectively. The total number of authors involved in these studies is 3502. While there are 66 single-authored documents, the number of authors for these documents is 71, indicating that some authors have multiple single-authored articles. On average, there are 4.51 authors per document. The percentage of authors with international collaborations is 22.29%.

Table 1. Main Information About Data

Timespan	2019:2023
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	165
Documents	951
Annual Growth Rate %	8.42
Authors	3502
Authors of single-authored docs	66
Single-authored docs	71
Co-Authors per Doc	4.51
International co-authorships %	22.29
Article	758
Editorial material	30
Review	103

Annual Scientific Production

There has been a change in scientific production from 2019 to 2023. The production started with 144 documents in 2019, increased to 226 papers in 2020, and as of now, 199 documents have been produced in 2023 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Annual Scientific Production

2nd European Congress of Health Sciences

May 4-5, 2024 - Bristow, VA / USA (ONLINE)
medjeur.com/congress

Oral Presentation-15 (continue)

Most Relevant Sources

In the field of missed nursing care, specific journals are prominently featured in the scholarly literature. The 'Journal of Nursing Management' leads with a significant contribution of 91 articles, making it the top-ranked journal in this area. It is followed by the 'Journal of Advanced Nursing' with 50 articles and the 'Journal of Clinical Nursing' with 41 articles (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Most Relevant Sources

Most Relevant Authors

Another crucial aspect of the bibliometric analysis conducted in this study is identifying the most influential authors in the field. For instance, Palese A stands out with 18 publications (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Most Relevant Authors

2nd European Congress of Health Sciences

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medjeur.com/congress

Oral Presentation-15 (continue)

Conclusions and Recommendations

This bibliometric study analyzed 951 studies published between 2019 and 2023, assessing the research on missed nursing care in intensive care units. The results indicate that the importance of Missing Nursing Care (MNC) in intensive care units is increasingly recognized. The majority of these studies have been conducted in the United States.

Among the keywords, the concepts of 'Care,' 'Impact,' and 'Nurse' have been particularly prominent. This emphasis reflects both the impact of MNC on patient care and the various ways it shapes the overall effectiveness of health systems.

This analysis sets a foundation for how MNC can be more effectively addressed in intensive care units and provides a basis for further research. Additionally, understanding the trends in practice and research in different countries significantly contributes to the literature, potentially enhancing the efficiency of global health systems in this area.

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2nd European Congress of Health Sciences

May 4-5, 2024 - Bristow, VA / USA (ONLINE)
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Oral Presentation-15 (continue)

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